

BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM: towards an integrated environment to support the design and construction of housing blocks

Leandro Madrazo, Álvaro Sicilia & David Pascual

ARC Arquitectura i Enginyeria La Salle, Universitat Ramon Llull, Barcelona, Spain

ABSTRACT: BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM is a computer aided design and building system for housing blocks built with industrialized processes. Architectural, building and computer-aided design systems have been conceived simultaneously as part of a comprehensive system. The architectural system is based on the aggregation of space-bars which can be combined into housing units. The addition of two kinds of bar – one containing building services and structure, the other free of both– gives rise to a multiplicity of flexible housing layouts which are generated by the computer system. Housing units in turn are assembled in linear blocks. For each block there is an indefinite number of possible facades made of freely arranged panels and openings. Facade compositions are created in an interactive way, modifying some specific design parameters (orientation, isolation, illumination, cost). The program automatically generates the documents for building a block (drawings, preliminary bills of quantities). The existing prototype consists of a generative application to create housing units, blocks and facades and an environment to visualize blocks in three-dimensions in the Internet. In the future, both applications –for generating and for visualizing– will be integrated in a comprehensive platform, which will support communication and collaboration among all agents involved in the design and construction of housing blocks: architects, manufacturers, contractors and occupants.

1 MASS HOUSING, INDUSTRIALIZATION AND ICT

Industrialized production of housing has been an enduring goal for the building industry, even before modern architecture assumed it as one of its programmatic objectives. As Stiller has recalled: “Long before the architects of the international avant-garde concerned themselves with the standardization and prefabrication of single-family houses, industry was exploiting factory-made building systems for simple forms of dwellings [...] For that reason, a purely architectural consideration of the subject is not adequate” (Stiller 1998). Nevertheless, the goal to achieve industrially produced housing has not been satisfactorily fulfilled yet, particularly from an architectural point of view. In the 1960’s, the problem of industrialized housing was described by Barr in these terms: “The essential problem [of the repetition of a limited number of basic dwelling forms] is how to combine the advantages of standardization, repetition and continuity of production with variety and freedom of choice for the individual” (Brookes et al. 1998). More flexible and neutral spaces can help to solve this problem. As Brookes & Vaughan

(1998) have contended: “Flexible space is, therefore, becoming paramount, as traditional forms of building are no longer able to solve modern problems”. The production of industrialized components, on the other hand, has been improving progressively, particularly with regard to building subsystems (Schulitz 2001). However, the architect’s main task –to devise complete systems integrating all the different subsystems– has not always been accomplished.

Far from being settled, industrialized production of housing must be once again rethought in the light of contemporary conditions. In today’s industrialized countries there is a need for flexible, industrially produced dwellings, which respond to social (family restructuring, mobile society, multi/intercultural), economic (part-time jobs, working at home, women at work) and technological (prefabrication, sustainability, ICT) demands. In this context of change, it is necessary to create dwellings with versatile layouts which can be transformed during the daytime to facilitate working at home, or become larger or smaller as the number of occupants change over time. In our increasingly dismembered and multicultural societies, it is also necessary to foster a sense of community, providing communal spaces also at the building scale. In order to make

sustainable buildings, it is necessary to employ construction systems which facilitate the maintenance and replacement of components (partitions, facades, technical services). And, to achieve all of these goals, it is necessary to integrate technology in a meaningful manner throughout the whole process: from design and construction (use of ICT to support the design process, prefabrication, and robotics), to performance control (energy), maintenance (facilities management) and demolition (sustainability).

In this scenario, ICT can become a decisive transforming factor, by providing computerized environments that support the design and construction of housing suited to the social, economic and technological needs of our time. Integrated, modular environments distributed throughout Internet would contribute to create more effective organizational structures which help to overcome the insufficiencies caused by the perennial fragmentation of the building and construction industry (Brown et al. 1996). Such environments could facilitate the emergence and consolidation of novel forms of collaboration among the different actors (architects, engineers, clients, contractors, and project managers) participating in a building's life cycle, from design to demolition.

This is the ultimate purpose of BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM: to create a web-based environment to support the design and construction of housing blocks with flexible dwellings, using industrial components, assembled according to the principles of open prefabrication.

2 INTERTWINING OF ARCHITECTURAL SYSTEM AND COMPUTER-AIDED DESIGN SYSTEM

With the early computer-aided integrated building systems created during the sixties and seventies, like OXSYS or HARNESS, a strong link was established between building with prefabricated components and computer systems. The benefits of linking both systems were, as Cross (1976) pointed out, that "Instead of the virtually infinite freedom of design in traditional building, the architect working with system building was constrained within a system boundary which could also be managed by the machine". However, the early computer-aided building systems were adapted to the existing building systems. With BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM, we have created both the architectural system and the computer program from scratch (Madrazo & Sicilia 2005). We did not go, as some of the early applications did, through a process of knowledge elicitation to extract rules from a building system with the intention to translate them into the computer (Eastman 1999). Rather, rules were already present in the conception of the architectural and building systems. For this

reason, it is difficult to establish what was first, architecture or computation, since architectural thinking and computerized procedures were closely interwoven right from the beginning.

This notwithstanding, and for purely descriptive purposes, we will consider BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM (www.barcodehousing.net) as being composed of three interrelated systems:

- 1 Architectural system, with housing layouts conceived as aggregations of space-bars which are then grouped in linear blocks.
- 2 Building system, which is based on industrially produced components, assembled according to principles of open prefabrication systems.
- 3 Computer-aided design system which allows users to explore, individually and in collaboration, formal and spatial configurations of housing units and blocks.

3 ARCHITECTURAL SYSTEM

BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM is a modular system based on a spatial grid of 120 cm. in the longitudinal dimension. The purpose of this grid is both to define a system of spaces as well as the positioning of physical elements (Habracken 1976). The dimension of the grid was set after a process of testing the flexibility of different layouts arrangements –at the level of the housing unit and at the level of the block– for different modules.

3.1 *Housing units*

At the outset, it should be noticed that the basic unit of composition of this architectural system is a space element rather than a set of building components. Housing units are the result of aggregating space-bars of one and two 120 cm. modules wide and 840 cm. deep. For each width, there are two kinds of bar: serving bars, including kitchen, bathroom and building services; and served bars, adjacent spaces which can be used for any other purpose (eating, sleeping, working...). While the dimensions of rooms in serving bars are constrained by the objects they contain (kitchen and bathroom equipment, bathroom, downspouts and ducts), spaces created by joining served bars can have flexible dimensions. Furthermore, spaces contained within a serving bar, other than kitchen and bathroom, can be absorbed by the served bars to make up other spaces.

One of the consequences of this spatial composition is the possibility to combine spaces in many different ways to create a large variety of housing units. Flexibility is, therefore, a characteristic of this spatial system. There is no standard-house for a standard-occupant. Rather, each housing unit can be configured combining space-bars in different ways

to accommodate the needs of different inhabitants. Furthermore, housing units can increase or decrease their size, by taking or giving away space-bars from or to the adjacent unit (horizontally and vertically). This way, a dwelling can easily adapt itself to the changing living conditions of the occupants throughout the life of the building (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Housing unit, as aggregation of space-bars.

3.2 Block

A block is the result of the aggregation of housing units (Fig. 2). However, the block has properties which are not inherited from the units and which makes the block a system of its own. For instance, to provide access to the units in a multi-story arrangement a 'block' has a circulation system, consisting of open staircases located at the interstices between units, connected to open walkways. The aggregation of units does not create the circulation system; rather this is part of the 'block'. Also, since the housing units are not self-bearing (walls are simply enclosing) their aggregation does not result necessarily in a stable construction. Therefore, the 'block' must provide a structure too. Altogether this makes the 'block' a 'support structure', as defined by Habraken (1972): "A support structure is a construction which allows the provision of dwellings which can be built, altered and taken down, independently of the others".

Figure 2. Block, as aggregation of housing units.

A system of connected open and semi-open spaces (stairs, terraces, roofs, corridors, platforms), strengthens the communal dimension of living in the block. For the same purpose, in a block there is a provision of spaces which can be temporarily occupied by tenants to be used as working spaces, communal services, storage or any other use.

4 BUILDING SYSTEM

The building system is based on open prefabrication methods, using components from different manufacturers (Fig. 3). In principle, the spatial configuration of the system can adapt itself to different forms of materialization using different construction systems and materials: prefabricated concrete, steel or wood for the structure; wooden, metallic or synthetic materials for facades.

Figure 3. Structure, facade and building services.

For this prototype version, certain types of materials have been selected. The main structural system is made up of pre-cast reinforced concrete members, with girders spanning 4.80 to 6.00 m. Floor slabs are made of pre-stressed concrete plates, 1.20 m. wide and 8.40 m. long. This pre-cast system makes it possible to use large spans, limiting the placing of columns on the facades. A secondary structural system for walkways and staircases is made of steel and anchored to the concrete structure.

Ventilated facades are built with resin panels and, eventually, photovoltaic panels. This layered facade, with an air gap, provides a good isolation both in winter and summertime. In the front facade, light protection is achieved with perforated panels and in the service facade with the shadow cast by walkways.

Building services run outside the block, under the walkways, entering the housing unit at the serving bars, through the suspended ceiling. This way, any service can be easily accessible from the outside and from the inside of the apartment, facilitating maintenance.

5 COMPUTER-AIDED DESIGN SYSTEM

As we started to create BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM, we wittingly forged a strong link between architectural and computer systems. At the early stage of development, our goal was twofold: 1. to come up with some design principles which could be “smoothly” moved on the computer 2. to integrate the procedures implemented in the computer in the design process.

Therefore, we could not make a clear cut distinction between the stages of designing the architectural system and programming the computer system: both were occurring simultaneously. For instance, by thinking of the floor plan as an aggregation of space-bars we pursued two goals, at the same time: on the one hand, to create flexible dwellings, and, on the other, to conceive a plan in such a way that would facilitate the subsequent application of space allocation techniques. This way rules did not have to be extracted from a previously existing building system, as was the case with OXSYS. Rather, rules were already present in the conception of the architectural system, so architectural design and computation became interwoven: design principles were tested against computer procedures before committing to a particular decision, and, conversely, ad hoc procedures were used during the design of the architectural system (for instance, to search for the most appropriate width for space-bars).

As architects, our role has been to create an architectural system rather than to design a particular building. In this regard, we have played the role of ‘system designers’, rather than ‘end designers’ (Gross 1996). After the rules and constraints implicit in the architectural system were made explicit to the computer, interacting with the computer program allowed us to unfold the potential of the architectural system, visualizing the undetermined number of solutions; a visualization task which, incidentally, could only be performed on the computer. From the point of view of systemic design, a housing unit or a block created by the computer program are not to be considered design products in themselves but rather the proof for the existence of an architectural system.

In its present implementation, BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM can be described as a procedural system operating on a finite number of spatial and building components. The generative process takes place at three different levels, in this sequence: generation of housing units, assemblage of blocks and composition of facades.

5.1 Housing unit generation

The generation process of a housing unit is divided in two stages: 1. generation of all possible space-bar combinations fitting within a given rectangular area,

and 2. for each possible space-bar arrangements, construction of valid layouts.

The first part of the process is an exhaustive search of the solution space, which can be automatically performed after setting a few constraints. The second one is a trial and error process seeking for a valid solution. This division of the layout generation in two distinct processes facilitates the implementation of some heuristic methods which are necessary to create a valid layout in the second stage. This splitting up strategy, which has the purpose of avoiding combinatorial explosions and optimizing the search process, is akin to the one first proposed by Steadman (1983).

5.1.1 Space-bars arrangement

In the first stage of the floor-plan generation, arrangements of space-bars are created for a given rectangular area. The generative process begins after setting the values for surface (sq. m.) and number of occupants. Given the limited number of possible arrangements, it is possible to perform an exhaustive search of the solution space, using an Iterative Deepening Search (IDS) procedure. A spatial allocation procedure is used to find out all arrangements of space bars within the given rectangular area, which fulfill the following constraints: 1. a rectangular arrangement must contain at least a double-module serving-bar 2. serving and served bars are placed alternatively and 3. if the number of occupants is larger than four, the layout must contain two serving-bars. The first constraint guarantees that any housing unit will have at least a kitchen and a bathroom. The second, prevents two serving-bars from being adjacent, to avoid concentration of services, and favoring the creation of versatile spaces by the subsequent layout generator procedure. The third one ensures that the number of bathrooms is the one required for the number of occupants.

5.1.2 Layout generation

The goal of the second stage of the floor-plan generative process is to create spatial layouts that fulfill the conditions established in a constraint model. A spatial allocation procedure is used to create valid spatial layouts for a given space-bar arrangement. In order to do that, the vertical arrangement is first divided horizontally into three zones. A similar division of a rectangular plan in three areas was proposed by Habraken (1976). The resulting rectangular cells can then be assigned a use or, alternatively, they can be used as spatial units to build multifunctional spaces (living and eating, working and sleeping).

This second stage is based on a heuristic method which guides the process of search. There are four different procedures involved, executed in the following order. First, the kitchen is inserted. The kitchen has to lie inside a double-module serving

bar, in an area next to the walkway. Second, the living areas are built up, adjacent to the kitchen, and also facing the walkway. A second procedure creates the living area, checking available spaces on left and right sides of the kitchen and choosing the largest free space. With the third procedure, bathrooms are placed. The orientation of bathrooms and the positioning of their doors take into account the adjacent living spaces, to avoid undesired visual contacts between the two spaces. Finally, with the fourth procedure, bedrooms are built with the remaining cells unused by serving and served bars. It starts by taking a cell inside a serving space-bar, to make it grow towards the left and right sides (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Generation of bedrooms.

The interface to visualize the floor plans is simple and straightforward. It consists of a set of sliders to visualize the valid plans the program has been able to generate under the specified conditions (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Interface for housing unit layouts.

What the user does with this interface is to search through the solution space for valid plans for a given arrangement of space-bars. The restrictions controlling this heuristic search guarantee all displayed floor plans are valid solutions. As Petrovic (1998) noticed, a user interacting with this kind of system is not able to distinguish between “designing” and “selecting”. Therefore, the “user” can be an architect searching and evaluating spatial arrangements or the

prospective inhabitant of the flat, who would choose the preferred layout among those the system is able to generate.

The housing units created in this interface are stored in the system to be used in the assemblage of the block.

5.2 Block assemblage

A block is the result of assembling a set of housing units in a previously defined volume. A user can define the shape of the block interactively using a set of sliders to define length, height and sections.

A block is generated in two steps: first, stairs are placed; then, housing units are inserted. Both generation processes are based on BFS techniques. At a particular level of the state-action tree, determined by a configurable value of depth K , the procedure evaluates the solution according to heuristic methods, and then backtracks to find the ‘best’ path to arrive at that solution (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Search process in the generation of the block.

5.2.1 Staircases

The process to place staircases begins after giving form to the volumetric envelope. Separation between staircases, and maximum and minimum distances from the housing unit to the stair, comply with local building codes. Accordingly, a procedure is used to insert staircases in the volume, in such a way as to guarantee that each housing unit will be accessible through walkways. Also, staircases are placed in a way that makes it possible to fill all the volume with housing units.

5.2.2 Housing units

The insertion of housing units begins after the staircases have been placed. In each insertion, the system checks the following: 1. there is enough space to insert the unit. 2. columns pass through a serving space-bar 3. distance to staircase is less than the maximum allowed and 4. there is a serving bar available above and below the unit for the building services to pass through.

Figure 7. Interface to create blocks.

The process of placing units in the block can be performed automatically or, alternatively, it can be under the control of the user. In this case, a diagrammatic representation is provided for the user to direct the process. It consists of a set of sliders to position the insertion node and to select the housing units to be placed (Fig. 7). If the user attempts to insert a housing unit in a place where there would be a conflict with the structure or which does not comply with the vertical alignment of building services, the system will reject it. In both cases, with or without the intervention of the user, the rules and constraints controlling the process are the same.

Blocks are stored in the database, and retrieved later to compose the facade.

5.3 Façade composition

For each block generated, it is possible to create an unlimited number of facades. In the existing prototype, the composition procedure is limited to the front facade. The composition of the facade is designed by the user in interaction with the system. There are two ways of composing a facade: 1. setting the spatial distribution and sizes of panels and openings and 2. assigning colors to panels.

The first interface (Fig. 8) is a set of connected circles, each one setting the values of a design variable: orientation, illumination, color, acoustics and cost. When the user modifies the values of these parameters the facade composition changes accordingly. For instance, if the facade is oriented to the south, the color of panels becomes lighter, since dark colors absorb more solar radiation. Moreover, it is possible to establish a link between design variables, simply by pulling a line connecting the centers of two circles. For example, if orientation is linked with illumination, when orientation changes, the amount of glazed surfaces will increase or decrease, depending if the facade is oriented towards the north or towards the south.

The second interface (Fig. 9) consists of a set of sliders, with which the color composition of panels

can be changed horizontally (all panels in the selected story), vertically (setting control points for the color distribution) and by housing unit (all units of the same size can be assigned the same color). With this kind of interface, the facade is designed by acting on the internal structure of its composition, rather than through the direct manipulation of its components. The interface, in this case, stands for an abstract representation of the façade –its inner structure or Gestalt– which makes the internal relationships ruling the composition intelligible to the user. It is a sort of representation which has no counterpart in other media, aside from the computer.

Figure 8. Interface to control the façade's design variables.

Figure 9. Interface to set color patterns.

6 WEB-BASED VISUALIZATION ENVIRONMENT

The application previously described is currently operating as a stand-alone programme. The outputs it creates are stored in a database, where each block is identified by a 14-digit number which stands for a bar code.

To visualize the blocks in Internet, we have created an ad-hoc environment which is a first step towards the creation of a more comprehensive platform that will support collaboration among all different actors involved in the whole lifecycle of a

housing block, from design to demolition. For the moment what we have achieved is a real-time translation of the outputs from the generative application onto a Lingo data model which can be visualized three-dimensionally in Internet using Macromedia Director.

In the current implementation of the web environment, a block is visualized with two-dimensional representations (floor-plans, facades) and three-dimensional models (exterior of the block and interior of the flats).

The three-dimensional model is represented in different ways: as a volumetric ensemble of housing types or bars; as an envelope made up of facades; and as structure made up of slabs, columns and girders. In each representation, the user can point to a component of the 3D model (a housing unit, a panel, a column) to get information about its characteristics (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. Block representation as façade envelope.

Walks through and around the block can be done automatically (the program creates the most adequate animation path for each block and for each flat) or can be created as the user moves in the scene. For this second case, sensors located at strategic points facilitate user-controlled navigation. By clicking in a portion of the façade corresponding to a housing unit, the camera is positioned at the entrance door of the dwelling. Once inside the flat, furniture pieces can be folded away, and partitions can be opened and closed so that the user can have an insight of the spatial possibilities (Fig. 11).

7 FUTURE WORK

In the development work to be carried out in the period 2005-2008, with the support of the Spanish National Plan for Research, Development and Innovation, the goal is to create an integrated web-based environment which supersedes the division between generation and visualization applications previously described. The goal is to create a modular, distributed environment, which supports collaborative

work during the whole project's lifecycle (Faraj & Alshawi 1999)

Figure 11. Interactive navigation inside a flat.

This integrated platform will facilitate collaborative work, a feature which is not yet supported by the prototype application. In the platform which is being currently developed, the generative system will be hosted in a .NET server which will also provide access to web services. This will allow, for example, a Macromedia Director application to access all functionalities of the system, avoiding the one-way translation of data between the generative system and the visualization environment, as is case now.

With a server-based application it will also be possible to run different processes simultaneously. For example, a process specialized in generating low-height blocks can be running at the same time as a process to generate towers. Another process which analyzes and classifies the outputs can be working in parallel. This way, the evaluation of design solutions can be better integrated in the generative processes. Moreover, the open architecture of the platform will enable different types of users to edit the design criteria (rules and constraints applied to the generation of housing units, blocks and facades) according to their particular expertise, something which is not possible with the closed structure of the existing prototype. Also, it will be possible to choose among different patterns of growth (for instance, to apply them to the generation of a block, to evaluate and compare the results) rather than sticking to a built-in procedure, as in the case of the prototype.

These classification processes will assign hierarchical tags creating sets of definitions, which are used by interactive interfaces to search and browse the space of design solutions in an intuitive manner. For example, the forms of blocks generated by the system can be identified by tags (e.g. U-shaped, L-shaped) so that a morphological classification of the block solutions becomes feasible. Then, an interactive interface would allow the user to search throughout a space of classified solutions, using the

tags as searching criteria. Tags are related to the kind of process that generates an output. Moreover, these interfaces will allow users to modify the vocabulary of tags generated by the system. This way, users would assign their own tags to objects (e.g. describing a block in a personal manner) or using tags previously defined by other users. This part of the research is taking into account previous projects carried out within the IST European research program dealing with the application of XML schemas to develop building and construction vocabularies, like eCONSTRUCT.

In the existing prototype, the building description is stored in an independent data model which is easy to transform as the project progresses. This custom data structure needs to be complemented with translators to communicate with third party applications (HVAC simulators, structural analysis, CAD packages) using IFC or .dxf formats.

An integrated environment like the one being devised for BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM should contribute to overcome the fragmentation of the construction industry. Integration means, in our case, to provide a computer-supported environment that facilitates parallel forms of collaboration among the different actors (designer-manufacturer-contractor-client) thus breaking away with the linear processes (from designer to contractor, from contractor to manufacturer) which characterize the design and construction of a building (Kalay 2004). In order to model the collaborative working processes, it is necessary to define the profiles of the different actors and their forms of interaction, as well as to create appropriate interfaces which make the processes visible and intelligible to the different participants (e.g. OSMOS, IST research project). This means to come up with a meaningful scenario where virtual teams are assembled to work throughout the whole lifecycle of the building –design, construction, maintenance, facilities management and demolition– with the support of the system.

It will also be desirable and coherent with the characteristics of the architectural system for different types of actors to contribute to the creation of a knowledge base as a result of their interaction with the system. This way we could move from the existing rule-based system onto a knowledge base system.

In particular, the participation of the future occupants in the composition of housing layouts, blocks and façade, is facilitated by the open compositional principles of BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM. For instance, the process of placing housing units in a block can be done collaboratively, as each prospective inhabitant chooses the location of the dwelling on a three-dimensional interface accessible in the web. This way, the ‘design’ of a block would be the result of the sum of individual decisions which would feed the generative process. In this

scenario, the architect would become a mediator in a collaborative design process, whose task would be to guide the system towards the creation of meaningful results.

In this open design process, manufacturers of building components should be able to check the ongoing design and make concrete proposals for facade components, for instance. Orders for prefabricated structural components could be launched directly from the building model to the factory, without the mediation of drawings. Virtual reality models could provide descriptions of the building model suitable for architects, clients and builders (e.g. Divercity, IST research project). All of this is feasible from the point of view of the technology, and coherent with the philosophy of the architectural, construction and computational systems.

8 CONCLUSIONS

We have described a prototype system to design and build housing blocks with industrialized methods which has been conceived from scratch as an interweaving of three different systems: architectural, building and computational. The existing computer implementation consists of two different platforms: a stand alone generative application and a visualization environment on the Internet.

Further development of this system pursues the creation of an integrated environment to support collaboration among all actors participating in the whole building’s lifecycle, from conception to demolition. The modular and distributed environment which has been outlined will conform to the fragmented nature of the building and construction industry whereas, on the other hand, it will facilitate the creation of working procedures and organizational forms that result from the parallel interaction among different actors and processes, overcoming in this way the linear processes and segmented procedures which have characterized the construction of buildings.

9 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work here presented was developed in the period 2001-2004 by the research group ARC Enginyeria i Arquitectura La Salle (www.salle.url.edu/arc), with the support of a grant provided by the Research General Plan from Enginyeria i Arquitectura La Salle, Universitat Ramon Llull. Leandro Madrazo, Eduardo Hernández, and Alfredo Peñafiel, architects, developed the architectural system. David Hidalgo, technical architect; Leonardo Correa, architect, and Isaac Martí, architecture student, collaborated at different stages of the project. The programming of the generative system

has been carried out by Alvaro Sicilia, Technical Engineer in Computer Science, using C++ and OpenGL. Printed documentation is produced exporting the data to AutoCAD. The web-based visualization environment has been programmed by David Pascual, Technical Engineer in Multimedia, using Lingo and Macromedia Director. The subsequent three-year development work started in January 2005, and it is being carried out by a team of researchers from Arquitectura La Salle, Universitat Ramon Llull, and the Department of Architectural Constructions from the Polytechnic University of Catalonia, coordinated by the research group ARC, with the economic support of the Spanish National Research, Development and Innovation plan.

REFERENCES

- Brookes, A. & Vaughan, N. 1998. Industrialized housing from the end of the Second World War to the present day. *Detail* 38 (5): 753-760.
- Brown, A., Rezgui, Y., Cooper, G., Yip, J., & Brandon, P. 1996. Promoting computer integrated construction through the use of distribution technology. *Electronic Journal of Information Technology in Construction* (1): 51-67.
- Cross, N. 1977. *The Automated Architect*. London: Pion.
- Eastman, C. 1999. *Building product models: computer environments supporting design and construction*. CRC Press: Boca Raton.
- Faraj, I. & Alshawi, M. 1999. A modularised integrated computer environment for the construction industry: Space. *Electronic Journal of Information Technology in Construction* (4): 37-52.
- Gross, M. 1996. Why can't CAD be more like Lego? CKB, a program for building construction kids. *Automation in Construction* 5: 285-300.
- Habraken, N.J. 1972. *Supports: an alternative to mass housing*. London: The Architectural Press.
- Habraken, N.J. 1976. *Variations, the systematic design of supports*. Cambridge: The MIT Press.
- Kalay, Y. 2004. *Architecture's new media*. Cambridge: The MIT Press.
- Madrazo, L. & Sicilia, A. 2005. BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM, a computer aided design and building system for housing blocks. In S. Sariyildiz and B. Tunçer (eds.), *Conference on Innovation in Architecture, Engineering and Construction (CICE); Proc. intern. symp., 15-17 June 2005*. Rotterdam.
- Petrovic, I. 1998. IT as design enabling technology. In M. Porada (ed.), *ECAADE, Computer Craftsmanship in Architectural Education; Proc. intern. symp., 24-26 September 1998*. Paris.
- Schulitz, H. 2001. Open and closed systems-an interview with Helmut Schulitz. *Detail* 41(4): 611-613.
- Steadman, P. 1983. *Architectural Morphology*. London: Pion.
- Stiller, A. 1998. Das Haus als Ware - Stationen auf dem Weg zur Produktion. *Detail* 38 (5): 748-752.